

ES30029 Final Year Research Project

Is a City Status Pointless?

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Abstract

The granting of city status in the UK is a tradition dating back hundreds of years; however, the benefits that come alongside it are unclear. It is commonly assumed that being labelled as a city has its advantages, yet very limited research has been carried out on the topic. This paper evaluates the impact of becoming a city on employment, gross value added (GVA) and tourism for two of the new cities granted in the 2012 Diamond Jubilee competition. The analysis in this study is carried out using a difference-in-differences approach, followed by two other statistical methods as checks. This paper finds city status to have had no significant effect on employment or GVA for these cities. However, the estimates suggest that city status has a large, positive impact on tourism.

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1 Introduction

People often associate city status in the UK with having a cathedral, university, or large population. However, any town can be granted city status in the modern day, and many apply for this civic honour in competitions that are run every few years. In 2022, Reading had their fourth bid for city status rejected despite there being no explicit benefits that come with it: no tax breaks, no funding, and “no extra powers beyond being allowed to put ‘city of’ on your street signs” (Elledge, 2022). Aside from a difference in title, the question is therefore raised as to whether any tangible benefits to becoming a city exist or if it remains an outdated, ‘pointless’ tradition. Some towns that have successfully bid for city status boast of the various benefits it has brought them; Perth claims it has seen its local economy expand 12% in the decade after its success in 2012 (Cabinet Office, 2022). Similarly, Newport deems its city status key to bringing the Ryder Cup to Wales in 2010 (Binding, 2017). However, there remains very little evidence as to what the actual effects of this civic honour are.

The first objective of this paper is to estimate the impact of city status on employment, gross value added (GVA), and tourism for the new cities granted in 2012. After collating various relevant data sources and using a variety of research methods, I conclude that city status has no significant impact on employment or GVA but may have a positive effect on tourism. The second objective of this paper is to understand why these conclusions might be the case, with the unclear selection process in city status competitions being a main driver behind the lack of impact. Musson (2012) carries out a similar analysis, which has been obtained through personal communication with Musson and is available as a working paper published in Public Sector Executive Magazine. Specifically, he focuses on the eight cities granted in 2000 and 2002, looking at five economic indicators. Beckett (2014) outlines the process of the 2012 city status competition and discusses arguments for and against the proposition that cities outperform non-cities, though he carries out no primary research.

This paper will be the most recent study evaluating the impact of UK city status benefits for ten years, therefore the findings may highlight differences in the importance of city status as of the last decade. Given the limited research in all fields regarding this topic, this paper will originally contribute to existing literature in a variety of ways, as discussed further in the literature review. This can be broadly separated into: (i) investigating the impact that city status has on tourism, which has yet to be done; (ii)

focusing on the impacts of cities granted in 2012, on which there has been no primary research carried out to date; and (iii) exploring the isolated impacts on towns of the bidding process for city status.

The remainder of this paper is organised as follows. In Section 2, background information for city status is outlined, with a particular focus on the 2012 city status competition. Section 3 provides an overview of the relevant literature. Section 4 describes the data sources and statistical methods used to evaluate city-status effects. In Section 5, the findings are presented and then discussed in Section 6. Section 7 provides a summary and concluding remarks.

2 Background

2.1 What is city status?

When a town in the United Kingdom becomes a city, it doesn't receive any special rights; it simply gets a change of title. Despite this, city status is still greatly sought after and can instill a sense of civic pride in the community to which it is presented. It has historically been granted by the monarch to a select group of communities, though the concept of cities in Britain has existed since Roman times, when they were initially named 'civitas' (Ross, 2023). There are currently 76 cities in the United Kingdom: 55 in England, seven in Wales, eight in Scotland, and six in Northern Ireland. [Table 1](#) and [Table 2](#) below present the five smallest and largest cities in the UK based on population:¹

Table 1: 5 smallest cities in the UK.

	City	Population	Country
1	St Davids	1,850	Wales
2	St Asaph	3,485	Wales
3	City of London	8,600	England
4	Wells	11,151	England
5	Armagh	14,749	Northern Ireland

¹ Population data acquired from the most recently available census data. See ONS; and <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/uk/>

Table 2: 5 largest cities in the UK.

	City	Population	Country
1	Birmingham	1,144,900	England
2	Leeds	812,000	England
3	Glasgow	635,130	Scotland
4	Sheffield	556,500	England
5	Bradford	546,400	England

It is a common misconception that city status is granted to places that have a cathedral; while this was historically true, it is no longer the case. A formal link between cities and cathedrals was established in the sixteenth century (Beckett, 2014). Specifically, in the early 1540s, Henry VIII founded dioceses², which were essentially six ‘cathedral towns’ across England that were all also granted city status. One can observe the presence of these dioceses in the modern day, as several UK cities which were granted hundreds of years ago remain relatively small due to being unaffected by population growth during the industrial revolution. For example, the English city Wells has a population of about 11,000 (see Table 1).

Between the 1550s and the 1830s, no new dioceses (and therefore cities) were created. This practise was revived in 1836, and large industrial towns continued to be overlooked by small towns which had a cathedral. Towns therefore began to petition the monarch directly for the city status. These claims resulted in Birmingham, Leeds, and several others being granted city status in the late nineteenth century (Beckett, 2014). In recent decades, city status has been granted by the monarch through a structured decision-making process, most often to mark significant royal events. Several competitions were held to celebrate milestones in the reign of Queen Elizabeth II, notably in 1992, 2002, 2012, and 2022. Other exceptions include a competition to celebrate the millennium in 2000 and awarding city status to Southend-on-Sea to commemorate the murder of their local MP, Sir David Amess, in 2021 (Elgot, 2021).

2.2 2012 Diamond Jubilee Competition

In January 2010, it was announced that a national competition for city status would be arranged to celebrate Queen Elizabeth II’s diamond jubilee. For this competition, bids

² A district under the pastoral care of a bishop in the Christian Church.

were to be submitted to the Department of Culture, Media and Sport (DCMS) instead of the Home Office, which was previously the case (Beckett, 2014). There have been no specific criteria for entrants to these competitions; the 2012 entry guidelines³ simply state that towns should demonstrate why they “deserve to be granted the rare honour of city status”. Within their bids, towns are to include a profile of the area, photographs of permanent features, and maps to outline where the ‘city centre’ sits within the local authority.

Table 3: Applicants in the 2012 competition for city status.

England				
Bolton	Bournemouth	<i>Chelmsford</i>	Colchester	Corby
Croydon	Doncaster	Dorchester	Dudley	Gateshead
Goole	Luton	Medway	Middlesborough	Milton Keynes
Reading	Southend	St Austell	Stockport	Tower Hamlets
Wales				
<i>St Asaph</i>	Wrexham			
Scotland				
<i>Perth</i>				
Northern Ireland				
Coleraine	Craigavon			

Note: Successful towns shown in italics

There were 25 applicants in total, and the three successful towns were announced in March 2012: Chelmsford, Perth, and St. Asaph. Only one title was expected initially; however, these three were awarded "in recognition of the significance of every part of the UK", and due to the "high quality" of bids submitted (Clegg, 2012). The successful and unsuccessful applicants can be seen in Table 3. These promotions were met with a mixed reaction from representatives of the above entrants. This marked Reading’s third unsuccessful bid, and Reading West MP, Alok Sharma (2012), expressed his disappointment and felt they had a strong case due to being “an economic powerhouse in the South East”. The decision also seemed to confuse Colchester MP, Sir Bob Russell (2012): “what the criteria was for an anonymous group of officials used to choose Chelmsford above other applicants, including Colchester, is something of a mystery”.

³ See <<https://committeeadmin.lancaster.gov.uk/documents/s22818/Civic-Honours-Entry-Guidelines.pdf%2030122010%20Management%20Team.pdf>>

Size of applicants was evidently not a key factor in the success of the three cities. This is demonstrated in Figure 1 below, which compares the size of the 2012 competition winners with three of the largest towns by population.⁴

Figure 1: Population of cities granted in 2012 vs large towns

3 Literature Review

This paper will examine the economic impact that city status has on the UK and determine to what extent it is ‘pointless’ in the twenty-first century. As part of Queen Elizabeth II’s Platinum Jubilee festivities in 2022, a record number of city status recipients (eight) were revealed. Several government departments and former winners claim that this accolade helps local economies in some way (Cabinet Office, 2022). However, these associated benefits are yet to be conclusively proven. There is very limited research within economics and other related fields on the effects of granting city status to a town in the UK. The true implications of city status are therefore important, as 38 towns applied in the competition for 2022 with the expectation of boosting their local economies and community spirits. Recognising the impact that city status has will ensure that local councils are better informed before entering this bidding process and committing a portion of their limited budget to this cause.

Musson (2012) is currently the only author who has carried out primary research into the possible effects of city status in the UK. His working paper examines the economic performance of the eight new cities created in 2000 and 2002 for their first five years of existence. His analysis uses five indicators to measure this: wages, unemployment,

⁴ Population data acquired from the most recently available census data. See ONS; and <<https://www.citypopulation.de/en/uk/>>

productivity, new firms, and investment. Musson (2012) finds that five of the eight new cities experienced relative growth in business investment, while six cities outperformed their region in reducing unemployment. However, new cities performed especially poorly with regards to increased wages. Therefore, he concludes that the overall evidence for the economic advantages of city status is limited. One concern with this study is that I do not have access to its full methodology, so it is unclear what statistical method Musson (2012) uses. However, given that the variables ‘new firms’ and ‘investment’ are analysed from 2000 onward, it would not have been possible to employ a difference-in-differences approach. To address this issue, this paper uses three statistical methods with data from several years before the relevant cities were granted their new city status. Another limitation in Musson’s (2012) research is that new cities are only compared to their ‘regional counterparts’, which could lead to skewed results due to the spillover benefits experienced by areas surrounding these new cities. Therefore, this paper will employ a control group consisting of a sample of all towns in the UK to mitigate this issue.

According to Beckett (2014), it is perceived to be the case, both historically and currently, that cities do better than non-cities. Beckett (2014) suggests that this stems from the Local Government Act of 1989, where local authorities were empowered to spend money directly on boosterism⁵. Local authorities began to see city status as a form of boosterism and a way of announcing to an international audience that their town was an important place with which they should be doing business. However, it is important to note that Beckett’s claim lacks empirical evidence, relying solely on economic theory. Whether cities do outperform non-cities in practice is difficult to gauge, partly because winners of city status competitions must convince their electorates that their efforts were worthwhile. For instance, following Sunderland’s success in 1992, the council leader Colin Anderson (2001) encouraged entrants in future competitions, as their new city “has boomed since” and “really made a big play on the fact that they are not a town anymore”. Beckett (2014) also acknowledges less measurable benefits of obtaining city status, such as the general buzz of local excitement as feelings of pride, community, and nationalism are generated by a symbolic event such as the success of becoming a city.

Various studies explore the inequality in economic growth between cities in the UK, which can help to infer how significant city status may be. Cities grow for multiple reasons, whereby some show sustained economic performance and others cycle up and down (Storper, 2013). Tyler et al. (2017) find the differential growth of both output and

⁵ The practice of actively promoting a city, region, etc. and its local businesses

employment across cities to be substantial between 1971 and 2014. Their findings indicate that the geographic location of a city has a clear impact on growth, with many of the fastest-growing cities situated in the southern half of Britain and most of the slowest-growing cities located in the north. This reinforces that factors beyond city status have a significant impact on economic growth. However, Tyler et al. (2017) do not define a city strictly as those who have been granted official status by the monarch, making it difficult to assess the immediate impact of city status. Although, one can deduce from their analysis that, on the whole, places with city status do not exhibit a higher growth rate than towns. This is because Tyler et al. (2017) find some towns, such as Reading and Chesterfield, to be "pulling ahead" of the national average GVA growth rate, while established cities such as Sheffield and Newcastle have consistently grown well below the national rate.

A large body of literature focuses on the reasons behind economic growth within cities, which also sheds light on the potential significance of city status as a driver of growth. Cities are more likely to experience economic growth due to agglomeration economies, which refer to the benefits that firms and individuals gain from locating in close proximity to each other (Glaeser and Gottlieb, 2008). Economic activities tend to agglomerate in a small number of places, typically cities (Fujita and Thisse, 1996). This can induce higher productivity for firms and workers as there are improved opportunities for sharing, matching, and learning (Graham and Gibbons, 2019). Thus, being granted city status may lead to agglomeration economies and the associated economic benefits. However, Roncolato and Kucera (2014) argue that "sustainable economic growth requires structural transformation", suggesting that city status is only likely to have long-term impacts if it results in structural changes.

The existing literature in this field has not explored any new cities since the ones established in 2002. A novel feature of this paper will therefore be the focus on local authorities that were granted city status in the 2012 competition, which provides an insight as to whether this tradition is still beneficial in the modern day. Musson (2012) also suggests that the process of putting together a bid for city status could be beneficial in its own right; however, he does not perform any statistical analysis to support this. Therefore, this study will also investigate the impact of the bidding process on unsuccessful towns to assess its effect on economic performance. Furthermore, the effect of city status on tourism remains unexplored in the literature, and therefore, this study will consider tourism visits as an outcome to measure.

4 Methodology

4.1 Conceptual Framework

This paper aims to measure the effect that city status has on: (i) employment; (ii) gross value added (GVA); and (iii) tourism in the new cities created in 2012 for their first seven years of existence⁶. Before describing the data and research methods used in the empirical analysis, I outline the conceptual framework guiding my interpretation. I start with the initial observation that city status is expected to attract more inward investment into an area compared to towns, as it is perceived that there is more opportunity to make money there (East, 2021). This, in turn, would generate more business opportunities, consequently resulting in higher levels of GVA and employment. Secondary economic benefits might include an increase in domestic and international tourism as a result of cultural investment or more simply due to Google trends (e.g., searching ‘best UK cities to visit’) (Doyle, 2021). Furthermore, the process of bidding in city status competitions often involves bringing community groups, businesses, and media together, which can be linked to regeneration and promotion programmes for the future (Musson, 2012). The hypotheses to be tested are as follows:

H_0 : Towns granted city status in 2012 saw no impact on the following outcomes compared to other towns: employment rate, GVA and tourism.

H_1 : Towns granted city status in 2012 experienced a rise the following outcomes relative to other towns: employment rate, GVA and tourism.

Table 4: Pre-treatment statistics in Chelmsford, Perth, and other UK towns.

	2012 Cities		Control Groups	
	Chelmsford	Perth	All towns	Unsuccessful Towns
Employment rate	0.769	0.751	0.727	0.705
Gross Value Added (£m)	3,937	3,297	3,730	5,726
Tourist trips (thousands)				
Domestic	214	-	237	311
International	-	68	72	75

Notes: These values are the means of each outcome in the data I have collected up to 2012. Refer to Section 4.2 for sources. ‘All UK towns’ represent a sample of 50 towns in the UK.

⁶ In the case of GVA, this is six years.

4.2 Data Sources⁷

Although three new cities were granted in 2012, this study solely focuses on the impact of city status on Chelmsford and Perth. The investigation of St. Asaph was not feasible due to its limited size and population, hence its exclusion from the analysis. At the time of this competition, the population of St. Asaph was merely 3,400 (Beckett, 2014, p. 12), which meant the data sources were not granular enough for its inclusion. For the analysis of employment and GVA, the data I use for the treatment area of Perth is representative of its local council area Perth and Kinross due to limitations in data availability. This should not compromise the validity of the analysis, as Perth is the largest city or town (by population) within this local authority by a substantial margin.⁸

Summary statistics of the pre-2012 outcomes are reported in Table 4, which separates between the two treatment groups and the two control groups used in the following empirical analysis. Employment rates were on average higher in Chelmsford and Perth compared to both control groups, confirming the evidence demonstrated in Figure 2. GVA levels in unsuccessful towns were significantly higher on average than the other groups; this is likely due to the inclusion of the London borough, Tower Hamlets. Tourism visits were lower in Chelmsford and Perth in comparison to the two control groups.

For the collection of employment data, I use the employment rate by local authority from the ONS annual population survey (APS), which also uses data from the Labour Force Survey (LFS). The APS consists of 12 months of survey data, broken down on a quarterly basis. Its purpose is to provide information on important social and socio-economic variables at local levels (ONS, 2012). I have collected data from 2007 (five years before city status was granted) to 2019 to ensure that the results are not skewed by the impact of COVID-19.

I use data on the GVA levels of local authorities, which is collected by the ONS. GVA is defined as the value generated by any unit engaged in the production of goods and services (ONS, 2023a). The GVA data used in this study is in current basic prices, as to not allow for changes in price over time. These GVA levels are 'balanced estimates', which are produced by combining existing income and production approaches using quality

⁷ APS extracted from Nomisweb: <https://www.nomisweb.co.uk/reports/lmp/la/contents.aspx>
GVA: <https://www.ons.gov.uk/economy/grossvalueaddedgva/datasets/regionalgrossvalueaddedbalancedlocalauthoritiesbynuts1region>

GBTS extracted from VisitBritain: <https://www.visitbritain.org/destination-specific-research>

IPS extracted from VisitBritain: <https://www.visitbritain.org/inbound-trends-uk-town>
⁸ See <https://www.citypopulation.de/en/uk/scotland/S12000048_perth_and_kinross/>

metrics. I have collected data up to 2018 as this is the most recent year provided in the dataset. In order to reduce the skewness of the data, all the data for GVA and tourism is transformed using logarithms.

Figure 2: Trends in employment rate, GVA, and tourist trips: Chelmsford & Perth compared to UK towns.

[Note: Tourism data for Chelmsford is domestic visits, data for Perth is overseas visits]

Collecting data at local authority level was challenging for tourism, as there was not a comprehensive database that included both Chelmsford and Perth, as well as the necessary other towns that made up the two control groups. Therefore, two separate datasets are used (one for each city), which allows the analysis to cover impacts on domestic and international tourism. For Chelmsford, I use visitor data from the Great Britain Tourism Survey (GBTS), which provides information about domestic overnight tourism by residents of Great Britain each year from over 15,000 respondents. A limitation of this dataset is that it only includes locations within England; hence, the control groups omit several towns that are in other countries and may not provide a comprehensive representation of the UK as a whole. Data from 2008 (earliest available in the dataset) up to 2019 is used in the analysis. For Perth, data from the International Passenger Survey (IPS) is used, which is a measure carried out by the ONS that collects information on passengers entering and leaving the UK. The IPS records the number of visits by overseas residents to UK towns and cities (ONS, 2023b). This dataset does not include an exhaustive list of UK towns, as some are grouped by county instead (resulting in Chelmsford's exclusion). This a limitation to my analysis as several towns in the two control groups are also not included, hence they are omitted from the analysis. I use data from 2009 (the earliest available data) to 2019.

4.3 Empirical Strategy

The main empirical goal of this paper is to evaluate whether UK towns granted city status in 2012 experienced an increase in employment, GVA and tourism. In order to achieve this, I employ three separate statistical designs, with the latter two used as robustness checks.

a. Difference-in-Differences

I first use the canonical Difference-in-Differences (DID) approach as a baseline method. To analyse a potential relationship between city status and the three outcomes, an estimating equation is defined as:

$$Y_{it} = \alpha_{it} + \beta_1 Post_t + \beta_2 Treatment_i + \beta_3 (Post_t \times Treatment_i) + \theta_i + \varepsilon_{it} \quad (1)$$

Whereby Y_{it} is the outcome of interest in local authority i in year t . $Post$ is an indicator variable equal to 1 if the time period is after city status was granted (post 2012), and 0 otherwise. $Treatment$ is an indicator variable for the treatment group, such that places within the treatment group are given a value of 1, and those in the control group are given a value of 0. The interaction term $Post \times Treatment$ is equivalent to an indicator

variable equal to 1 for observations that are in the treatment group, for the time period after 2012; thus β_3 is the coefficient of interest. θ_i refers to city fixed effects.

There are two time periods and two groups in the baseline DID set up. The treatment group (new city) is exposed to treatment in the second period but not the first, and the control group (other towns) is not exposed to treatment during either period. A key assumption of this method is that, in the absence of treatment, the average outcomes for treated and control groups would have followed parallel paths over time – known as the parallel trends assumption (Calloway and Sant’Anna, 2021). I use canonical DID methodology given that the treatment time is the same for both treatment groups. Accordingly, it is not necessary to construct control groups to address the bias from time-varying treatment effects, as discussed by Goodman-Bacon (2021).

In [Table 5](#) below, I examine two places that become cities in 2012, treating each city separately, as in a case-control study. In [Table 6](#), both new cities are combined into one treatment group. There are two main control groups in this analysis: (i) a sample of all other towns in the UK (control group 1); and (ii) UK towns that bid unsuccessfully in the 2012 competition (control group 2). Within control group 1, there is a sample of 50 towns across the UK, accounting for a variety in population, geographic location, and wealth. I have used a sample for control group 1 as it was not feasible include an exhaustive list of all UK towns due to the large quantity and consequent data collection limitations. The incorporation of a control group 2 enables us to examine the potential effects of the bidding process on the relevant outcomes.

To control for unobserved time invariant factors, I include city fixed effects for the DID specification. In doing so, the analysis is able to capture variables impacting employment, GVA, or tourism that remain constant across time but vary across different cities. However, Angrist and Pischke (2008) highlight the common issue of attenuation bias arising from measurement error in fixed-effect estimates.

There is a burgeoning literature highlighting the limitations of the DID approach and its assumptions. For instance, Bertrand et al. (2004) argue that the parallel trends assumption is restrictive. This can be a result of extrapolation bias, which may arise when untreated UK towns show different pre-2012 trends compared to their treated counterparts (cities). As illustrated in [Figure 2](#), the trends in tourist visits in Chelmsford were different from those in other UK towns even before it was granted city status in 2012. In order to increase the similarity between treatment and control local authorities,

I supplement the DID analysis using both the synthetic difference-in-differences method (SDID) and a synthetic control approach (SC).

b. Synthetic Difference-in-Differences

Arkhangelsky et al. (2021) developed the synthetic difference-in-differences method as a new estimator which builds on insights behind both DID and SC methods. It can be interpreted as a unit and time weighted version of the standard DID estimator, which matches pre-exposure trends to weaken the reliance on the parallel trend assumption. Similar to an SC approach, we begin by finding weights ($\hat{\omega}^{sdid}$) to align pre-2012 trends for the control groups with those for new 2012 cities. In this case, there are N towns in a balanced panel, whereby N_{co} (control towns) are not granted city status while the last $N_{tr} = N - N_{co}$ (treated) towns are granted city status from 2012 onwards. Following from formula (1), SDID ensures that:

$$\sum_{i=1}^{N_{co}} \hat{\omega}^{sdid} Y_{it} \approx N_{tr}^{-1} \sum_{i=N_{co}+1}^N Y_{it} \quad (\text{for all periods pre 2012}) \quad (2)$$

The weights above are then used in a basic two-way fixed effects regression to estimate the average causal effect of city status (see Arkhangelsky et al., 2021). Arkhangelsky et al. (2021) find that this method is competitive with (or dominates) DID and SC in applications where they have respectively been used in the past. This implies that SDID can be used in the same contexts as the other specifications and may potentially give more accurate estimates

c. Synthetic Control Approach

The synthetic control approach was first introduced by Abadie and Gardeazabal (2003) and Abadie et al. (2010). Using this method, we also construct synthetic counterfactuals by weighting local authorities in a control group in order to match the pre-2012 trends of Chelmsford and Perth. These weights are chosen so that the resulting synthetic local authority best replicates the values of a set of predictors for each respective outcome before new cities were granted in 2012. There is a substantial body of research on which controls to include as predictors when using a synthetic control approach (for instance, see Kaul et al., 2015). I have chosen to use the pre-treatment path of the outcome variable as an economic predictor for each respective outcome.

5 Results

5.1 Baseline Results

Table 5: The impact of city status on employment, GVA and tourism: Difference-in-Differences estimates.

	No Fixed Effect						City Fixed Effect					
	(1) Emp. (C1)	(2) Emp. (C2)	(3) GVA (C1)	(4) GVA (C2)	(5) Tour. (C1)	(6) Tour. (C2)	(7) Emp. (C1)	(8) Emp. (C2)	(9) GVA (C1)	(10) GVA (C2)	(11) Tour. (C1)	(12) Tour. (C2)
Panel A: Chelmsford												
β_3	0.007** (0.003)	0.003 (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.011)	-0.037** (0.017)	0.025 (0.032)	0.077 (0.061)	0.007** (0.003)	0.003 (0.005)	-0.040*** (0.012)	-0.037** (0.018)	0.025 (0.033)	0.077 (0.064)
Observations	598	221	546	234	456	204	598	221	546	234	456	204
R-squared	0.047	0.135	0.028	0.020	0.003	0.008	0.699	0.776	0.98	0.986	0.918	0.929
Panel B: Perth												
β_3	0.005 (0.003)	0.001 (0.005)	0.078*** (0.011)	0.081*** (0.017)	0.069 (0.059)	0.028 (0.094)	0.005 (0.003)	0.001 (0.005)	0.078*** (0.012)	0.081*** (0.018)	0.069 (0.061)	0.028 (0.097)
Observations	598	221	546	234	209	154	598	221	546	234	209	154
R-squared	0.037	0.095	0.027	0.027	0.014	0.034	0.695	0.763	0.980	0.986	0.922	0.937
Notes: Difference-in-differences regressions. Robust standard errors in parentheses, where *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. All coefficients are rounded to 3 decimal places. (C1) denotes control group 1 and (C2) control group 2. Columns on the right (7-12) represent results for city fixed effects.												

The limited literature on this topic suggests that there is some economic benefit to being granted city status, which is partly contradicted in this section. Table 5 presents estimates of the impact of city status on the two treatment groups (Chelmsford and Perth), using the DID specification. Table 6 shows estimates of the impact of city status on both Chelmsford and Perth combined, to be one treatment group.

Regarding the impact of city status on employment, there is a small, positive effect on both Chelmsford and Perth; however, it could be argued this is unsubstantial. For instance, in column (1) of Table 5, β_3 is 0.007, thus there is a 0.7 percentage point increase in employment for Chelmsford compared to all towns, which equates to a 0.9% increase. In Perth, there is a 0.5 percentage point (almost 0.7%) increase compared to all towns, though this effect is not statistically significant. Musson (2012) found employment to increase in 6 out of the 8 cities he investigated, however these increases were of a far greater magnitude – Musson found a 10% increase in Inverness compared to other towns in its region. For both cities, I also find that the increase in employment is relatively smaller when comparing to towns who unsuccessfully bid in 2012 (instead of a sample of all UK towns). Columns (1)-(2) in Table 6 show the combined increase on employment to be 0.4 percentage points greater when comparing to all towns, suggesting that the bidding process itself leads to a small increase in employment levels.

Columns (3)-(4) in Table 5 reveal that city status has contrasting impacts on the GVA levels of Chelmsford and Perth. In comparison to both control groups, city status has a positive and statistically significant (at the 1% level) impact on the level of GVA in Perth. These are substantial increases of 7.8% and 8.1% compared to all towns and unsuccessful towns, respectively. However, Chelmsford's GVA levels decline relative to all towns and unsuccessful towns (both statistically significant). The effect on GVA for both new cities combined can be observed in columns (3)-(4) of Table 6, showing an approximately 2% increase in GVA levels compared to both control groups; however, neither of these estimates are statistically significant. Notably, it cannot be concluded with certainty that city status has a positive impact on GVA, as it was associated with a negative effect on GVA for one of the two cities analysed. This disparity in the post-2012 trends for GVA levels between Chelmsford and Perth may be attributable to external factors influencing economic growth occurring at the time; sub-section 6.4 explores this possibility further.

This analysis finds city status to be positively associated with tourism visits for both Chelmsford and Perth under the DID specification, though this effect is not precisely estimated. In Chelmsford, there is a substantial increase in domestic tourist visits of 7.7%

compared to unsuccessful towns. Similarly, in Perth, there is an increase of 6.9% in visits by overseas residents compared to a sample of all towns. The trend of tourist visits before and after Chelmsford and Perth were granted city status is shown in [Figure 2](#). In the case of Chelmsford in particular, the pre-2012 trends are not parallel, as Chelmsford experienced a significant decline in visits between 2008 and 2011, unlike other towns in the UK. This failure of the parallel trends assumption motivates the use of synthetic control methods and synthetic difference-in-differences in the robustness checks section of this paper.

Table 6: The impact of city status on employment and GVA: Difference-in-Differences estimates (Chelmsford and Perth combined).

	(1) Emp. (C1)	(2) Emp. (C2)	(3) GVA (C1)	(4) GVA (C2)
Post xTreat	0.006*	0.002	0.019	0.022
	(0.003)	(0.005)	(0.044)	(0.046)
Observations	611	234	559	247
R-squared	0.052	0.165	0.028	0.029

Notes: Robust standard errors in parentheses, where *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. All coefficients are rounded to 3 decimal places. (C1) denotes control group 1 and (C2) control group 2. Note: Tourism results are not included as different datasets are used for Chelmsford and Perth.

Columns (7) to (12) in [Table 5](#) present the city fixed effects of city status. There is no change in effect on any of the three outcomes for both Chelmsford and Perth once time invariant characteristics are accounted for. There is only a marginal increase in some of the standard errors for the city fixed effects estimates. Therefore, there does not appear to be any differing effect of city status on employment, GVA, or tourism.

5.2 Robustness Checks

[Table 7](#) presents the synthetic difference-in-differences regressions for the three outcomes. For the most part, these results are similar to those calculated using a DID specification in [Table 5](#), proving that they are robust to the parallel trends assumption. However, all but one of the estimates below are statistically insignificant. Graphs showing the weighted units under the SDID method are presented in [Figure 3-14](#) in the appendix.

Table 7: The impact of city status on employment, GVA and tourism: Synthetic Difference-in-Differences estimates.

	(1)	(2)	(3)	(4)	(5)	(6)
	Emp. (C1)	Emp. (C2)	GVA (C1)	GVA (C2)	Tour. (C1)	Tour. (C2)
Panel A: Chelmsford						
Post x Treat	0.005 (0.026)	0.011 (0.015)	-0.042 (0.082)	-0.025 (0.063)	0.174 (0.181)	0.348** (0.157)
Observations	598	221	546	234	456	204
Panel B: Perth						
Post x Treat	0.003 (0.026)	0.003 (0.015)	0.065 (0.082)	0.079 (0.063)	0.136 (0.230)	0.154 (0.289)
Observations	598	221	546	234	209	99
Notes: Synthetic difference-in-differences regressions. Standard errors in parentheses, where *** p<0.01, ** p<0.05, * p<0.1. All coefficients are rounded to 3 decimal places. (C1) denotes control group 1 and (C2) control group 2.						

The average treatment effects for the treated subpopulation (ATT) presented in columns (1)-(2) show that city status has a small, positive (but economically insignificant) impact on employment, matching the results in Table 5. The general effect on GVA is also similar under the SDID specification [see columns (3)-(4)], once again finding a positive impact on GVA in Perth and a negative one in Chelmsford. The only difference being that in Perth, GVA seems to have increased by a greater amount when compared to unsuccessful cities than to all towns. However, it is worth noting that no estimates for employment or GVA in either city are statistically significant.

Our results for tourism in Table 5 are not robust to the parallel trends assumption, which is expected given the pre-2012 trends in Figure 2. City status is once again shown to have a positive effect on tourism for both Chelmsford and Perth, however this effect is far greater under the SDID specification. In Chelmsford, I find the effect on domestic tourist visits to be a 17.4% increase in comparison to unsuccessful towns. This is even larger when compared to all towns, with an increase of 34.8%; which is significant at the 5% level. However, it is possible that these are slightly biased estimations due to the extreme difference in pre-trends for tourist visits in Chelmsford, as illustrated in Figure 2. This may be the case as the SDID method does not completely remove the reliance on the parallel trends assumption; it only weakens it (Arkhangelsky et al., 2021). In the case for

Perth, city status also seems to evoke a greater increase in international tourist visits. In general, the estimates under the SDID specification are a more reliable indicator of the impact city status has on tourism as it allows the parallel trends assumption to hold.

I carry out a further robustness check by repeating these results once again using a synthetic control approach. These results are illustrated in the graphs found in [Figures 15-26](#) in the appendix, which present the trends of each outcome when compared to synthetic UK towns in each control group. By using this method, I also find that the results under the DID specification for employment and GVA are robust. Similar to the findings under the SDID specification in [Table 7](#), the SC approach finds that city status has a large positive impact on tourist visits for both cities, however these are statistically insignificant.

5.3 Further Limitations

An evident limitation of this paper's methodology is that the analysis focuses on just two treatment cities (Chelmsford and Perth) due to the omission of St. Asaph. The use of a relatively small number of treatment groups presents a greater risk of bias in the results, as Chelmsford and Perth may not be representative of the larger set of cities that have been granted in recent years. This also poses a difficulty when generalising results in the conclusion, as it is hard to judge the overall effects of city status based on just two case studies. Extending the analysis to include successful cities across multiple competitions (dating back to 1992) would allow us to explore the effect of city status in a broader historical context.

Secondly, there are a relatively small number of observations when comparing cities to towns that unsuccessfully bid in 2012. There were 22 unsuccessful towns in total; however, some had to be omitted due to granularity issues in the available data. Some estimates may therefore be insignificant due to limited data reducing their statistical power, as opposed to the absence of a genuine relationship. A further impact of this can be the over-fitting of regressions, leading to overly optimistic R-squared values; however, as evidenced earlier in this section, the R-squared values are not unusually high.

In a similar vein, using a sample of 50 other towns in the UK may expose the results to sampling bias, whereby they may not be fully representative of the full population of British towns. Despite accounting for a variety of population, geography, and wealth in this sample, it may still be skewed towards an unaccounted-for characteristic. This may lead to uncertainty in the inference of the results as the estimations are only an

approximation of the true population parameters. With regard to future research, it would be helpful to extend this analysis to use a control group that includes an exhaustive list of all UK towns, which may require a longer amount of time or improved datasets.

6 Discussion

6.1 Why is city status pointless in the UK?

As they do not publish specific criteria, very little is known about how the DCMS and ultimately the monarch choose between bidders in city status competitions. This has led to the selection of numerous small and unlikely towns over the past few decades, which has often sparked reactions of surprise. The absence of economic benefits arising from city status may be attributable to the selection of towns not being based on any material criteria such as size or scope for economic growth. For instance, St. Asaph's mayor, Andrew Thomas (2012), put their success down to it being the only one of 22 ancient cathedral dioceses never awarded city status. It is therefore possible that the DCMS prioritises factors like the presence of a cathedral ahead of how well a town is set up for growth. This came at a time when Reading, which is predicted to be the UK's 3rd fastest growing local authority economy by the end of 2023, was denied (CEBR, 2022). This raises the argument that what may once have been a meaningful indicator of size or status in the sixteenth century is now an outdated tradition. There are several examples of towns such as Bournemouth and Reading who have been comfortably attracting investment for several years despite their lack of city status, suggesting this is not such a crucial criterion for investors (Elledge, 2022).

In addition, Beckett (2014) explains how the becoming of a city has always been no more than a "status thing", with there never actually having been any privileges involved in winning. Therefore, quite simply, in the absence of any guaranteed investment, tax cuts, or prize money, there is no explicit cause for city status to result in any economic benefits. There is also nothing preventing any town from adopting the 'city' title themselves. For example, in 1856, the Burgh of Dunfermline resolved to use the title of 'city' in all official documents, despite never being officially recognised. A spokesperson for the Lord Chancellor's office (2002) described this as a "discourtesy to the Queen", before Dunfermline acquired legitimate city status in 2022. The ability to do this undermines the prestige of city status, as any town could theoretically enjoy the benefits associated with being a city.

Even though some evidence suggests that being a city brings economic benefits, this may not be the case in reality for a number of reasons. Firstly, as Musson (2012) discusses, the increasingly competitive nature of the city-granting process in the last few decades means bidders must talk up the importance of becoming a city, even if the actual evidence for this is limited. This ‘evidence’ often takes the form of quotes from local councillors, many of whom were involved in the campaign to win city status to begin with, hence it may suffer from confirmation bias. Secondly, as austerity measures and other economic challenges arise, local authorities’ finances are placed under significant pressure, making it crucial that their money is spent efficiently (National Audit Office, 2021). Therefore, when local authorities are trying to justify their bids for city status, they may be under increasing pressure to do so in clear economic terms as opposed to less tangible benefits in order to avoid scrutiny. As noted by Waitt (2001), these less tangible benefits can come in the form of civic pride and excitement within communities. For example, following their success in 2022, Colchester organised a programme of events so that “everyone can celebrate Colchester’s first year as a modern city” (King, 2023). It may therefore be unfair to look solely at economic benefits when discussing the purpose of city status, as it is possible that the government maintain this tradition purely to boost the morale of communities.

6.2 Why might city status increase tourism?

Our results indicate that becoming a city increases tourist visits in both a domestic and overseas context. As no literature to date has explored the impact of city status on tourism, I analyse the potential reasons for this positive association.

A likely effect of city status is a sense that the chosen local authority is ‘put on the map’, as a result of the increased publicity it brings. Prior to their bid in 2021, Wrexham Council published a list of potential benefits to becoming a city, which included “greater awareness” of their history, culture and language. This may directly boost tourism in new cities and may also cause increases in Google searches for those cities. Furthermore, online tourism platforms may be more likely to include cities in their recommendation lists; for example, Chelmsford and Perth were named in the Guardian’s ‘Top 10 British city breaks for both culture and outdoor fun’ in 2021. Havraneka and Zeynalov (2019) find that Google trends information for a destination is a useful tool when predicting the actual number of tourist arrivals, such that an increase in Google searches is associated with an increase in tourist visits. When analysing the Google trends for the new cities granted in

2012, I find that Chelmsford experienced a 24% increase in average Google searches in the four years following the announcement.⁹ This effect is likely to be even greater for smaller cities with less of an online presence; for instance, searches for St. Asaph almost tripled in the month immediately after.¹⁰ These observable increases in Google trends may therefore be a significant factor driving the increase in tourist visits discussed in Section 5.

Secondly, when towns bid in city status competitions, they often include ambitious investment plans for the future in order to be competitive, which in turn may attract more visitors. In the case of Chelmsford's application,¹¹ they vowed to build a new £65 million railway station to the north of the proposed city centre, thus making it a more accessible place for tourists to visit. In addition to this, their bid discussed a provision for up to 100,000 square metres of new retail floorspace in the proposed city centre, which would significantly add to the attractions on offer to tourists. Whilst it could be argued that these benefits are purely a result of the bidding process itself and therefore not associated with the change in status, the results indicate that the control group of unsuccessful bidders experienced no economic benefits compared to all other towns. We must also consider that the tourism benefits experienced by Chelmsford and Perth may not be as significant as the results suggest, as there does not seem to be a visible increase in related economic factors. It would be expected that a significant rise in tourist visits would create a large number of jobs in the area for example, however there are no significant increases in employment observed for either city.

6.3 Alternative strategies for local growth - The Preston Model

For local councils aiming to boost their economies, there are more effective initiatives to consider than bidding to become a city. In this sub-section, an alternative strategy known as the 'Preston Model' is discussed, which has proven to be successful.

Preston attracted very little inward investment between 2004 and 2008 and suffered heavily from the 2008 financial crisis. This resulted in austerity measures and severe budget cuts for local authorities. In an effort to tackle the economic challenges faced by the city, Preston entered a strategic partnership with the Centre for Local Economic Strategies (CLES) to begin harnessing the potential of anchor institutions in what was

⁹ See: <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=all&geo=GB&q=%2Fm%2F017_4z&hl=en-GB>

¹⁰ See: <https://trends.google.com/trends/explore?date=all&geo=GB&q=%2Fm%2F02t3_x&hl=en-GB>

¹¹ See: <https://www.whatdotheyknow.com/request/547722/response/1314790/attach/3/Chelmsford%20City%20Bid%20Document%20May%202011%20web.pdf?cookie_passthrough=1>

coined 'The Preston Model'. The CLES modelled this reform on "community wealth building", a model previously developed in Cleveland, Ohio, by The Democracy Collaborative (Centre for Public Impact, 2018). Anchor institutions are large, public, and not-for-profit institutions rooted in local communities (Hanna, 2019); from 2013, Preston engaged several anchor institutions to collaborate in this initiative (including Preston City Council, Lancashire County Council, and Preston's College). They encouraged these anchor institutions to purchase services and supplies locally, which results in money being recirculated in the community at a greater rate than money spent with large, extractive corporations. This causes a multiplier effect, which can create more jobs, greater tax revenues, better public services, and more prosperous communities (Hanna, 2019).

Within just a few years after changing the local procurement processes in Preston, the initiative was widely regarded as a huge success; Jeremy Corbyn (2016), the Labour Party leader, praised it as a model town for economic development. In 2016, three years after the initiative began, £74 million had been redirected back into Preston and a further £200 million in the wider Lancashire area. This also led to further benefits, such as a reduction in unemployment from 6.5% in 2014 to 3.1% in 2017 and being named the "most improved city in the UK" in 2018 (CLES, 2019). This initiative has been significantly more successful in boosting a local economy than that of achieving city status, as it is a more calculated approach that does not solely rely on a change of title.

6.4 GVA growth in Perth

Our results in Section 5 show that in terms of GVA, Perth performed significantly better than other UK towns after 2012, whilst Chelmsford performed marginally worse. As of 2021, Perth boasted growth of 12% in the past decade and had a productivity level 17% higher than the Scottish average (Scottish Cities Alliance, 2023). As each of the two new cities show contrasting trends in GVA, it is reasonable to assume that city status has no real impact on GVA, and that this difference in economic growth is caused by other factors. Since 2012, Perth has invested heavily in various development and infrastructure projects, which may partly explain why their economy has performed especially well.

For example, Springfield Properties submitted plans to build 3,000 new houses in a £1 billion development for Bertha Park Village, in 2015 which were accepted, and construction began soon afterwards (Buchan, 2017). The Perth Transport Futures project is another major infrastructure initiative that aims to improve transportation in and

around Perth and promote economic growth.¹² The project consists of a number of key elements, including the construction of the Cross Tay Link Road, a new road bridge over the River Tay that will connect the A9 to the A93. Zhang and Cheng (2023) find that investment in transport infrastructure has a promotive effect on economic development in the UK; thus, such a project would have likely boosted economic growth in Perth. It could therefore be assumed that investment initiatives like these would more likely be responsible for the sharp increase in GVA than city status.

7 Concluding remarks

This paper evaluates the impact of city status on employment, GVA and tourism for new cities granted under the 2012 Diamond Jubilee Competition. The results show that city status has no effect on employment or GVA, despite a common goal of bidders in these competitions being to improve these indicators. However, this study finds city status to have a positive effect on tourism. This was the case when comparing new cities to a sample of all UK towns, and towns that bid unsuccessfully in the 2012 competition. It is also discovered that these conclusions hold true when accounting for city-fixed effects. The null results for GVA and employment are robust when using other statistical methods. When carrying out robustness checks on the results for tourism, I find that through the use of other statistical approaches, the positive impact of city status on tourism increases further. The process of putting together a bid for city status itself is found to have no significant effect on its local authority.

Establishing why city status might have no impact on employment and GVA is a further contribution of my work. The unclear, outdated decision-making in the city status competitions seems to be a key factor that may hinder any potential benefits. Many towns without city status comfortably attract investment and are growing quickly, which indicates it is not such a crucial criterion for investors or economic growth.

Despite the lack of evidence for the economic importance of becoming a city, there do appear to be some less tangible benefits, such as civic pride and excitement. This may justify a reason for the government to continue with this tradition, as it is a way that they can boost the morale of communities without spending any money. I believe that future research would benefit from carrying out a similar empirical analysis on the eight new cities granted in 2022. This is because there is currently a very limited body of literature

¹² See <<https://www.perthtransportfutures.co.uk/>>

on this topic, and it may be easier to generalise the effects of city status when looking at a larger number of treatment groups.

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9 Appendix

Synthetic Difference-in-Differences weighted trend graphs:

Figure 3: Employment rate in Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 4: Employment rate in Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 5: Employment rate in Perth vs all towns

Figure 6: Employment rate in Perth vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 7: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 8: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 9: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Perth vs all towns

Figure 10: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Perth vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 11: Domestic visitors (thousands, in natural logarithm form) for Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 12: Domestic visitors (thousands, in natural logarithm form) for Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 13: Overseas visitors (thousands, in natural logarithm form) for Perth vs all towns

Figure 14: Overseas visitors (thousands, in natural logarithm form) for Perth vs unsuccessful town

Synthetic control method: Graphs illustrating post-city status trend estimates:

Figure 15: Employment rate in Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 16: Employment rate in Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 17: Employment rate in Perth vs all towns

Figure 18: Employment rate in Perth vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 19: GVA in Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 20: GVA in Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 21: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Perth vs all towns

Figure 22: GVA (in natural logarithm form) in Perth vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 23: Domestic visitors for Chelmsford vs all towns

Figure 24: Domestic visitors for Chelmsford vs unsuccessful towns

Figure 25: Overseas visitors for Perth vs all towns

Figure 26: Overseas visitors for Perth vs unsuccessful towns